

Girls Education: Challenges and Opportunities in Uttarakhand, with the Special Reference to Bageshwar

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Abstract

In the developing world, women and girls are denied opportunities in society and education. Educating a girl is very beneficial and one of the best investments. It is very sad that in India girls' education is neglected, lack of education limits the prospect of decreasing family income and put woman and girls in a gulf of trafficking and exploitation. There are many reasons –poverty, social factor, marriage at tender age, unawareness, Geographical conditions burden of household work, etc. The present report has been prepared to analyze the progress of girls' education in India, Uttarakhand, and Bageshwar. The study covers the period from 2011 to the present and is primarily based on secondary data collected from the census report 2011, and the investigator used different types of articles, books, and online material for data collection. India is a country where the sex ratio is rapidly deteriorating (918:1000 per census (2011), the sex ratio in Uttarakhand is 963 girls per 1000 boys and in Bageshwar sex ratio is (1090: 1000 per census 2011) In India and Uttarakhand sex ratio is deteriorating, it affect many factors but primarily girls education in every part of the country and Uttarakhand the ratio of girls education is less than boys and in Bageshwar sex ratio is 1090 girls per 1000 boys it's really appreciating. The literacy rate In India as per the census 2011, the male literacy rate is 82.14 and the female rate is 65.46 there is a vast gap of 16.68%. In Uttarakhand as per the census 2011, the literacy rate is 78.82 %, the male literacy rate is 87.40, and the female literacy rate is 70.01% the gap between them is 17.39%, it also high. In Bageshwar as per the census literacy rate is 80.01% higher than in India and Uttarakhand, the male literacy rate is 92.33 % and the female literacy rate is 69.03%, there is a vast difference of 23.03%. So we can say that there is a vast gender difference in accordance with education and girls are deprived to get an education and still deteriorating. So the Government of India and the state government are trying to increase the level of education and quality education for girls education in India placed in the concurrent list of the constitution through 42 amendment act in 1976, it is a joint responsibility of the center and state government (Snehi, 2007) national policy of education 1986, the plan of action 1992 followed by the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan in 2001. There are many other programs as such – NPEGEL, Kasturba Awasiya Vidhalay, Mid-day Meal, RTE Act 2009, Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao Abhiyan 2015, (BBBP) scheme was launched on 22 January 2015 by Narendra Modi. It aims to address the issue of the declining child sex ratio image. There are many scholarships provided by the central government and state government. But the status of girls' education is still unchanged. So the educationist should be aware of the specific needs of the girls. There are formed many commissions and committees to increase enrollment in girls' schools but it is still decreasing. So this paper is an attempt to discuss the challenges and opportunities in the field of girls' education.

Keywords: Education, Girls Education, Gender Difference, Challenges, RTE.

Introduction

According to Mahatma Gandhi, " If you educate a man you educate an individual, but if you educate a woman you educate an entire family."*our predominant patriarchal system does not provide enough chances to have education even if they wish. Girls should be motivated to take up education.

Educating girl is very beneficial and one of the best investments for a prosperous family, society, and country. It is disappointing that in India girls' education is neglected.

Jyotirao Phule and his wife were the pioneers of girls' education in India. Savitribai was fond of teaching, she trained at Ms. Farar's Institution in Ahmadnagar and Ms. Mitchell's school in Pune and became the first female teacher who inspired young girls of her time to peruse education. Jyotirao Phule along with his wife founded the first woman's school at Bhidewala in Pune in the year 1848, at a time when the right of Women was almost nonexistent. She is called the mother of girls' education in India. Iswar Chandra Vidhyasager in Calcutta and many other reformers in Mumbai set up schools for girls. Recently the Government of India and the state government are trying to increase the level of education and quality education.

Education in India was placed on the concurrent list in the Indian constitution through the 42nd Amendment Act. It is a joint responsibility of the central government and state government. The National policy of education (1986), The program of education (1992) followed by the SSA in 2000-2001. There are many other programs such as -NPGEL, Kasturba Awasiya Vidhyalay, RTE 2010, and Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao Abhiyan 2015 are working for minimizing gender inequality and paving way for girls' education. It is very important to educate girls to empower and improve their status in society.

How many effects are needed may be judged from the literacy rate given in the tables below.

TABLE-01 : Sex Ratio

India		Uttarakhand		Bageshwar	
Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
1000	918	1000	963	1000	1090

TABLE-02 : Literacy Rate in India

Census	Peron's	Male	Female	Male Female Gap
2011	74.04	82.14	65.46	16.68

TABLE-03 : Literacy rate in Uttarakhand:-

Census	Peron's	Male	Female	Male Female Gap
2011	78.82	87.40	70.01	17.39

TABLE 04: Literacy rate in Bageshwar

Census	Peron's	Male	Female	Male Female Gap
2011	80.01	92.33	69.03	23.30

Block Wise Literacy rate in Bageshwar:-

These tables indicate that there is large inequality in gender. Girls' education is deteriorating as per the census of 2011. Table 1 shows that the sex ratio in India is 918 girls of 1000 Boys, in Uttarakhand 963 Girls of 1000 Boys, and in Bageshwar 1090 girls of 1000 boys. In India and Uttarakhand the sex ratio is deteriorating and in Bageshwar girls are more than boys.

The literacy rate in India as per the census 2011, the male literacy rate is 82.14 and the female rate is 65.46 there is a vast gap of 16.68%.

In Uttarakhand as per the census 2011, the literacy rate is 78.82. The male literacy rate is 87.40 and the female literacy rate is 70.01 the gap between them is 17.39% its also high.

In Bageshwar as per the census 2011, the literacy rate is 80.01 which is higher than in India. The male literacy rate is 92.33 and the female literacy rate is 69.03 there is a big difference of 23.30%. So, we can say that there is a vast gender difference on the basis of education, and girls are deprived to get an education and still deteriorating.

Objectives

1. To assess the progress of girls, education.
2. Elaborate on the programs and policies of the government for girls' education.
3. Discuss the challenges.

Methodology

The study covers the period 2011 to the present and is primarily based on secondary data collected from the census report 2011.

Challenges

Although many programs and policies are being conducted by the Indian government to check the problems of girls' education, girls remain undereducated and the government is failed to provide quality education to girls.

There are many challenges in the way of girl education they are as follows:

1. Social Barrier:- Actually this is not a barrier but people made it a barrier they think that girls should be avoided to go to school, they traditionally think over it and are denied to get girls education and protested the girls' education. In the backward Kapkote block of Bageshwar district, the situation is still unchanged.
2. Some schools are very far from the village and it is difficult to reach there, and back home daily.
3. There are some villages where a separate school for girls does not exist. In the farthest villages of Bageshwar is a lack of girls' schools, especially in Supi, Saurag, and Khati areas of Kapkote.
4. The major barrier in the way to girls' education is the early marriage of girls. In the farthest villages mindset of the people is still unchanged, they think that girls should be married early. Most girls got married in their childhood or at a tender age.
5. They have a burden or responsibility of their younger brother and sister, the elder girls take care of their sisters and brothers. And they have to do all the household chores.
6. Poverty is another reason-Direct and indirect costs of school education prevent the girls from education and families are not able to afford that cost.
7. In the farthest villages of Bageshwar, there is a lack of woman teachers and girls feel hesitant to go to school.

Opportunities:

Major programs and policies have been made to improve the educational scenario for girls. Education is a tool for the prosperity of the nation, state, society, and family.

Central and State governments enacted many programs and policies for girls' education as follows:

Programs and policies of Center Government

Programs	Policies
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dhan Laxmi Scheme 2. The Incentive to Girls/ NSIGSE 3. National Means Cum Merit Scholars Programmes (NMMSS) 4. M.D.M 5. CBSE scholarship scheme 6. Sukanya Samridhi Yojana 7. Balika Samridhi Yojana 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Article-15 2. constitution amendment act-42 3. NPE 1986 4. SSA 5. NPEGN 6. Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya 7. Rashtriya Madhyamika Shiksha Abhiyan 8. Right To Education Act 2009 9. Beti Bachao Beti Padhao 2015 10. Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan 2018

Article 15 of the Constitution: Article 15 states that no discrimination can be made on the grounds of religion, race, caste, sex, and place of birth, the article gives favorable statements in support of a girl child. It is general agreement that girls' education needs special attention in the context of the country's development and as an important sector of our society. (Das and Mohanty, 2009)

Education is placed on the concurrent list: Through the 42nd constitutional amendment act in 1976 education is placed on the concurrent list. Education is a joint responsibility of the center and state governments. The main purpose of this effort was to ensure uniformity in the education system for better utilization of funds, and supervision from the union government.

National Policy of Education: In 1986 the National Policy of Education was founded by Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi. This policy recommended a lot for girls' education.

Plan of Action 1992: The education policy as modified in the year 1992 stated that free and compulsory education of elementary level children up to the 14 C (Bhopal, 2009) this policy provided equal opportunity to boys and girls.

Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan: Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan is a campaign started by the state government of India in 2000-2001 to achieve the objectives of universalization of education at the elementary level. It has given special emphasis on girls' education. Its main aims are i) Free textbooks for boys and girls ii) Separate toilets for both girls and boys.

National Programme for Education of Girls at Elementary Level: In September 2003 NPEGL launched a new program to provide supplementary support for enhancing the education of underprivileged girls at the primary level.

Mid-day Meal Scheme: This popular scheme was launched in 2005 to provide nutritional food for all the school-going children up to the 8th class. The scheme has become very conducive to ensuring the enrollment of students in government schools.

Beti Bachao Beti Padhao: This campaign was started by govt. of India by Prime Minister Narendra Modi in 2015 with an initial fund of rs. 100 crore. (Wikipedia)

Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya: KGBV is a scheme for the girls to the schedule caste and schedule Tribe and OBC girls, which was launched in July 2004 for setting up of residential school upper primary level.

National Merit cum scholarship Programme: It is a centrally sponsored scheme of the MHRD govt. of India conducted every year by the science branch of the Directorate of Education Delhi in the month of November for the students studying in class 8th of govt. or aided school.

National Scheme of Incentive to Girls for Secondary Education: It is a centrally sponsored scheme with the objectives to establish and enable the environment to reduce dropouts and to promote the enrollment of girl children mainly belonging to SC and ST girls in secondary schools.

CBSE Scholarship Scheme: This Scheme is a central government scheme for a single girl child to boost girl education in India. The objective of the scheme is to give more relaxation in school tuition fees.

Sukanya Samridhi Yojana: This is a famous center government scheme for single girl children the government scheme for girl children is a part of The Beti Bachao Beti Padhao campaign. The objective of this scheme is to save the girl child and provide better education and secure good future.

Nanda Devi Kanya Yojana: Nanda Devi Kanya Yojana is an amazing initiative by the Uttarakhand government, this scheme was launched in 2018 with the help of the women and child welfare department. This scheme focuses on financial help to girls at the time of their studies after school.

Suggestions for Improving Girls' Education:

At last, it is well established that girls' education is still a challenge in our country to cope with this very problem first the infrastructure should be improved and the parents of the girl children to be counseled to foster the girls for education. It is a moral duty of every parent to send their children to school, child-centered classrooms with adequate learning and teaching facilities should be established. Woman teacher can understand the girls' problems easily so more and more women teachers should be appointed. Sports should be organized for girls so that they can be promoted to be leaders and improve their confidence and motivation. More and more schools should be opened for girls. In the remote areas of Kapkote and other hillsides, every school must have a proper facility of hostel for girls so that the girls from the interior region can comfortably pursue their studies.

Conclusion

The above study shows the vulnerable condition of girls' education in India especially in the village areas of the country, though much more efforts have been made to improve the condition of the girl children, much more to be done practically to improve the educational condition among the half population. If the various programs and policies made for the same are implemented honestly the situation is sure to improve. The administration and the government should undertake every step in this direction, as women teachers are being appointed the number of girls enrollment is increasing and they are feeling comfortable in the schools.

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